

Narcissus and Echo, content and learning, meanings and belongings: a decolonial possibility in school spaces

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The school system constitutes a hierarchical, colonial and exclusive space that maintains an unequal society and that reinforces privileges of some over others. Content and learning ideas are central to their configuration. With this scenario, we produced in this essay a possibility for school spaces, from a decolonial reading of Grada Kilomba, in his interpretative performance of the Greek mythology Narcissus and Echo. Images, sketches and clippings of texts are constituents of this narrative. An alternative, in the midst of what happens in this school system, can be constructed from a decolonial discussion of education (mathematics), through the ideas of meanings and belongings.

*While I write,
I am not the 'other' but the self,
not the object but the subject.
Grada Kilomba*

Grada Kilomba, a Portuguese artist based in Germany, held in 2017 an exhibition at the São Paulo Biennial with the following title: Illusions Vol. I Narcissus and Echo. In an artistic way of revisiting and reinventing some myths that constitute relationships and affections in our contemporary society, Kilomba invites to produce other relationships and other affects, which serve as inspiration in the writing of this narrative. It is an invitation to a decolonial production that problematizes two protagonist "actors" in the school: the contents and the learning. Through compositions with the performance of Grada Kilomba, in the midst of images, clippings of her writings and doodles, we produced a narrative and other possibilities to interrogate school mathematics contents and learning.

1. INTRO		
I was invited		And I often feel,
to come here today.	I often have this feeling	that we all know
But, I actually feel	that everything was already said.	everything already.
there is nothing new		We just tend
I can say.		to forget it.

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Image 1: World invitation (Adapted from *Desobediências poéticas* de G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*. p. 62)

Narcissus

In the 16th century, Caravaggio painted a narcissus in love with his image. In the spell given by Nemesis, the goddess of judgment, this young man should love someone who would never love him back. With few possibilities, one and only one was present in his life: to love his own image.

Image 2: Narcissus (from *Narciso*, Caravaggio de M. Imbroisi; S. Martins, 2019. *História das Artes*. In: <https://www.historiadadasartes.com/sala-dos-professores/narciso-caravaggio>)

Grada Kilomba writes:

PART II	<i>Narcissism,</i>
VIII.	<i>narcissism is the</i>
<i>Narcissus,</i>	<i>love directed towards</i>
<i>Narcissus became</i>	<i>the image of oneself,</i>
<i>a metaphor</i>	<i>it is the excessive admiration</i>
<i>for someone who takes itself</i>	<i>of one's self appearance,</i>
<i>and its own body,</i>	<i>and the incapacity to love</i>
<i>as the object of love.</i>	<i>or acknowledge others</i>
	<i>as objects of love.</i>

Image 3: Narcissus (*Desobediências poéticas* by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*. p. 71)

Unfolding this reading of Narcissus, we have a contemporary society at different levels and intensities, with subjects manufactured under this logic. Going a step further, the Myth of Narcissus does not only refer to people, but also to systems and, in our reading, to the school system. This hierarchical, colonial and exclusionary system that maintains an unequal society and that reinforces privileges of some people over others (Quijano, 2005; Walsh, 2013; Tamayo, 2017; Giraldo and Fernandes, 2019). It is evident that these inequalities are produced in different ways and scales. An example would be a small city in the global north, in a rich

country, compared to a small city in the global south, in a poor country. However, when producing a global reading of our society, we see that it is strongly marked by economic inequalities, structured from binarisms, exclusions, misery, wars, climate crises, etc. Just as an example, COVID-19 is a symptom of this global society. It's not a problem. The global economy is not in crisis due to the pandemic. It is the economic, social, political and climatic relations between humans and non-humans that produce this symptom of our global society (Lugones, 2014).

Image 4: Narcissus and school (Desobediências poéticas by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*, p. 55)

In the school system, mathematics occupies a prominent place, sometimes considered the most valued discipline that ultimately defines who will be excluded or included (Bishop, 1999; Walsh 2009). Mathematics in the classroom is constituted by contents ordered in a hierarchical manner, linearly, from simpler to more complex processes. Mathematics in the classroom is often closed on itself. Some things can be said, through predefined rules and processes. Other things cannot be said, because there is no definition, axiom, theorem, corollary or property that allows to speak. School mathematics often seeks a fixation of its own image.

Image 5: Narcissus as a school system (Desobediências poéticas de G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*. p. 48)

Sometimes, assessment practices materialize at school through content and the students' learning of this content. Content and learning assume a unique place in the discussion about education, compose the matrix of a colonial process, it constitutes political strategies for a system closed in itself, a system passionate about its image, constituted by eurocentric patterns, which overlap its modes of know everyone else (Quijano, 2005). The limit of the school, and of the whole school system, is making students learn content in the hope that, with that, it will be possible to build another society. Hope is an affection of stagnation, dissatisfaction as a structure of enjoyment and paralysis of subjects in schools.

I live in a space of timelessness.
An empty space.
a white space,
a white infinity
a 'white cube'.

A 'white cube'
that presents itself as
absent of color
and of meaning.

Image 6: Space (Desobediências poéticas de G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*. p. 75)

Echo

But the story of Narcissus cannot be told without the story of Echo, as Grada Kilomba warns us.

Image 7: Echo and Narcissus (Desobediências poéticas by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*. p. 50)

One day, Hera, goddess who protects marriage and fertility, was looking for her husband Zeus, god of gods, sovereign, who was having fun with nymphs. Echo, in an attempt to protect Zeus, engaged Hera in a long conversation, so that Zeus had time to escape. Faced with this attitude of Echo, Hera cursed the nymph with the following spell: Echo, who loved to speak, could now just repeat the last words she heard. The nymph would never say a word of her own again. Soon, Echo fell in love with Narcissus and, being unable to speak a word,

she lived in hiding looking and contemplating her passion. One day, given an opportunity by Narcissus' speech, Echo repeated his words, corresponding to his expectations. Composing with Grada Kilomba:

Image 8: Echo (Desobediências poéticas by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*, p. 76)

Echo authorizes Narcissus' speech. She sustains and maintains Narcissus' wishes. In our reading, Echo is constituted in the evaluations that take place in the mathematics classrooms, evaluations of the students' learning that reproduce the consensus projected by the system and that in the end make the system stay as it is, maintaining its current power structure. The school system produces some success and excessive failure and operates with no voice, no questioning from those who live and follow the rules and make other movements unfeasible. Echo, too, constitutes, in our reading, the external comparative evaluations of school systems, which are carried out in a naive movement in search for quality in education, in a comparison between students from different countries, even though this assumption is never made explicit by the students and by the international assessment systems.

Learning assessment in mathematics is a research theme in the area of Mathematics Education, which presents different possibilities for teachers to carry out other assessments in the classroom, such as an assessment as a research practice (Buriasco; Ferreira; Ciani, 2009, Esteban, 2001), an assessment for learning (Fernandes, 2009), the investigation of students' errors, as pedagogical possibilities for the teacher's work (Borasi, 1985, Viola dos Santos; Buriasco, 2008). However, all these practices are limited by the learning of students' content, or even the production of other dynamics in the classroom. They operate in a logic of improving the classroom, as well as the system, the progress and development of students and their knowledge in schools. Echo, that is, the evaluations that take place in schools have little impact on structural changes in our society. As we read in Grada Kilomba:

Image 9: Echo (Desobediências poéticas by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*, p. 76)

The colonial project of (mathematics) education

Narcissus and Echo, according to our read of Grada Kilomba, help us to problematize the mathematics classroom and the assessments that take place there. Our problematization focuses on the content and learning. Perhaps, these are the strongest products of a colonial project¹ and the organization of a society that has the school as a space for the reproduction of its logic, affections and knowledge.

In our contemporary society, fabricated by surveillance capitalism, increasingly violent in relation to the ways of coexistence between humans and non-humans, we have a school that is often constituted as a hierarchical, binary and exclusionary system (Quijano, 2005; Walsh, 2013; Tamayo, 2017; Giraldo and Fernandes, 2019). Some characteristics of the contemporary school education appear democratic in access, in opportunity, in quality and in the production of knowledge for an entire development of the human being, assuming a character of universality. However, we are still guided by the assumptions of a (mathematics) education project that highlights traits of Eurocentrism and operates with the effects of coloniality (Quijano, 2005).

In this school, subjects are sometimes constituted as objects, such as those in which “reality is defined by others and identities are created by others” (Kilomba, 2019, p. 28). With Narcissus and Echo, we read this school as a place where it operates in reproduction and repetition actions, cast by rules, regulations and guidelines, designed by a strategic system that only reflects its images.

Concerning the [epistemological and hegemonic] (mathematical) knowledge that constitutes this school, Walsh (2009) states that it often feeds and maintains the oppressive structures of society, due to the conditions of production and because it is impossible for students to propose authentic explanations to the reality that surrounds them. They also reduce their possibilities of problematizing structures and inequalities that make up their lives and that of their families. In this way, school denies differences and operates as a place of exclusion, even when students learn mathematical content “well”. In terms of Grada Kilomba:

Image 10: Disruption (Desobediências poéticas by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*, p. 72)

¹ I speak of a colonial project in the direction of that opera with effects of coloniality. By coloniality, with Quijano (1997), I understand it as something that transcends particularities and maintains the logic of historical colonialism relations, which does not disappear with the end of the colonial experience, with independence.

Our argument is that the school is limited to discussions about content and learning. Other discussions unfold from this, but content and learning are still central. This limitation causes the school system to be constituted in a narcissistic way and that the evaluations that take place in the school spaces are reinforcement for the maintenance of this system, like the nymph Echo.

Discussions about different ways of organizing ourselves with nature, about the relationship between humans and non-humans, the affections and feelings that move us little to deal with global problems, such as: misery, climatic crises, deforestation of our forests, pollution of our rivers, the neglecting of refugee crises, the extermination of indigenous populations, the prejudices still very present in our relations, the idea of women still as a subordinate, submissive and violated human being by the idea of men, etc. are still little moved in spaces schoolchildren. Often, they can even be inspirations for some projects, but the final target is the mathematical content and the learning of it by the students. Again, in resonance with Grada,


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It remains then a simple question:  
which role do we choose to play?  
  
The role of Narcissus,  
not to know.  
The role of Echo,  
not wanting to know.  
Their obedience,  
that we should not know.  
Or knowing,  
what we since long know.
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Image 11: Know (Desobediências poéticas de G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*. p. 77)

For (mathematical) educations with decolonial attitudes: Meanings and belongings

An alternative to this scenario would be producing educational spaces based on the concepts of meanings and belongings. Not an alternative, in the direction of replacing what happens in schools. Much less as a salvation. An alternative that can be combined with what happens in schools, but that produces a process of deconstruction of these educational systems and, with that, possibilities for the construction of other affects, logics and knowledge. It is an alternative with a decolonial attitude, which puts ideas like improvement, progress, development on hold. It produces tensions, sparks, other effects with schools in a colonial project (mathematics) education. From Walsh, we assume the term decolonial in the direction

of not eliminating or silencing the colonial, but acting on the fissures as a place of production of possibilities, in becoming. That is,

I do not intend to simply disarm, undo or reverse the colonial; move from a colonial to a non-colonial moment, as if it were possible that the employers' traces would cease to exist. The intention, instead, is to accentuate and provoke a positioning - a continuous posture and attitude - to transgress, intervene, insurgent and influence. (Walsh, 2009, pp. 14–15).

We speak of possibilities as an invitation to production/action, as “insurgent practices that fracture modernity/coloniality and make possible other ways of being, thinking, knowing, feeling, existing and living with” (Walsh, 2013, p. 19). Operating in a space of possibilities is “[...] creating another way of understanding, another way of articulating knowledge, practices, [and] subjects” (Santos, 2007, p. 39), who “have the right to define their own realities, to establish their own identities, to name their stories” (Kilomba, 2019, p. 28).

In this article, in the form of a narrative, we displace and discuss the characteristics of mathematics education in the school system with a decolonial attitude (Walsh, 2013). We do not intend to explaining a research object, present a theoretical framework, follow a methodological procedure and with that, present some considerations from an analytical movement. Our production, our theorizing process, invents itself in a narrative that unfolds some considerations, provokes some affections, and invites the reader to produce with us. It is not about presenting closed arguments, but invitations. It is not about producing explanations, but rather about bringing researchers into processes of inventing concerns. For this reason, we use Grada Kilomba's performances with photos, aphorisms, poems and writings. Some attitudes of decolonial productions in mathematics education that come close to our essay may be the works of Carolina Tamayo (2017) and Victor Giraldo and Filipe Fernandes (2019).

Meanings² produced by students, which are invented in their stories and life experiences, as a possibility to produce economic, political and cultural organizations in schools. A school, a mathematics classroom built on the basis of a political project in which the whole community is part of it and where the processes of producing meanings of the members of that community constitute a point of reference for this political project. Of course, that knowledge constructed and systematized by society, can also be part of this political project, but not as a centrality. For example, the idea of making decisions in different situations can be a starting point for building activities in which students can produce knowledge, narratives and affections. Making decisions does not constitute content, but rather an invitation, as a process of producing meanings of students and teachers (Lins, 2005; Viola dos Santos; Barbosa; Linardi, 2018; Paro; Viola do Santos, 2019).

Belonging could be another idea in the production of schools amid decolonial attitudes. It is not a matter of focusing on students' learning of certain processes of producing meanings, nor of evaluating those processes. It is about producing, carrying out maintenance,

² Meanings is a notion of Model of Semantic Fields (Lins, 2001, 2005, 2012; Oliveira, Lins, 2002). Just one draft, /.../ 'Meaning' is characterised as what a person actually says about an object, in a given situation (activity); but it is not everything that a person could eventually say about that object (Oliveira, Lins, 2002, p. 2)

deconstructing certain processes of belonging of students and teachers in certain educational spaces. Economic, political and cultural conditions are central to the discussion and problematization of processes of belonging. Collectivity and uniqueness of students and teachers are two sides of a coin that are tense at all times. The demands that provoke movements in schools (processes of producing meanings and processes of belonging of students and teachers) are directly related to the lives of these students and teachers, in an attempt to produce readings from the global issues of our society.

Wars, hunger, climatic crises, dehumanization, that is, human and non-human relationships in the Anthropocene, can constitute a possibility for the production of meanings and belongings in school spaces. The verb to learn would be just one more in schools, in compositions along with the verbs to imagine, to dream, to smile, to cry, to move, to create, to relate ...

Narcissus and Echo, school and evaluations, students and teachers, families and communities, human and non-human, in crossings that produce other space-time materials, are invented in other modes of life production, always in an invitation, between meanings and belongings.

Image 12: Producing (*Desobediências poéticas* by G. Kilomba, 2019, *Pinoteca de São Paulo*, p. 58)

References

- Bishop, A. J. (1999). *Enculturación matemática: La educación matemática desde una perspectiva cultural*. Paidós.
- Borasi, R. (1985). Using errors as springboards for the learning of mathematics: An introduction. *Focus on Learning Problems in Mathematics*, 7(3-4), 1–14.
- Buriasco, R. L. C., Ferreira, P. E. A., & Ciani, A. B. (2009). Avaliação como prática de investigação (alguns apontamentos). *Boletim de Educação Matemática*, 22(33), 69–96.
- Esteban, M. T. (2001). *O que sabe quem erra? Reflexões sobre avaliação e fracasso escolar*. DP&A.
- Fernandes, D. (2009). *Avaliar para aprender: Fundamentos, práticas e políticas*. Unesp.

- Giraldo, V., & Fernandes, F. (2019). Caravelas à vista: Giros decoloniais e caminhos de resistência na formação de professoras e professores que ensinam matemática. *Perspectivas da Educação Matemática*, 12(30), 467–501. <https://doi.org/10.46312/pem.v12i30.9620>
- Imbroisi, M. & Martins, S. (2019). *Narciso, Caravaggio*. História das Artes. <https://www.historiadadasartes.com/sala-dos-professores/narciso-caravaggio>
- Kilomba, G. (2019). *Memórias da plantação: Episódios de racismo cotidiano*. Cobogó.
- Kilomba, G. (2019). *Desobediências poéticas*. Pinacoteca de São Paulo. http://pinacoteca.org.br/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/AF06_gradakilomba_miolo_baixa.pdf
- Lins, R. C. (2001). The production of meaning for algebra: A perspective based on a theoretical model of semantic fields. In R. Sutherland, T. Rojano, A. Bell, & R. Lins (Eds.), *Perspectives on school algebra* (pp. 37–60). Kluwer.
- Lins, R. C. (2005). Categories of everyday life as elements organising mathematics teacher education and development projects. In IMU Secretariat (Ed.), *15th ICMI Study Conference: The professional education and development of teachers of mathematics*. <https://www.mathunion.org/icmi/conferences/icmi-study-conferences/icmi-study-15-conference-proceedings>
- Lins, R. C. (2012). O modelo dos campos semânticos: Estabelecimentos e notas de teorizações. In C. L. Angelo, E. P. Barbosa, J. R. Viola dos Santos, S. C. Dantas, & V. A. Oliveira (Eds.), *Modelo dos campos semânticos e educação matemática: 20 anos de história* (pp. 11–30).
- Lugones, M. (2014). Rumo a um feminismo descolonial. *Estudos Feministas*, 22(3), 935–952.
- Oliveira, V. A., & Lins, R. C. (2002). *On the production of meaning for the notion of linear transformation in Linear Algebra: Kika and Vivian speak*. Heraklion.
- Paro, J. C., & Viola dos Santos, J. R. (2019). An activity based on an everyday life category and the movements in a mathematics teacher working group. In J. Subramanian (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Tenth International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (pp. 662–670). MES10.
- Quijano, A. (1997). *Colonialidad del poder, cultura y conocimiento en América Latina*. Amatua.
- Quijano, A. (2005). Colonialidade do poder, eurocentrismo e América Latina. In E. Lander (Ed.), *A colonialidade do saber: Eurocentrismo e ciências sociais – perspectivas latino-americanas* (pp. 107–130).
- Santos, B. S. (2007). *Renovar a teoria crítica e reinventar a emancipação social*. Boitempo.
- Tamayo-Osorio, C. (2017). A colonialidade do saber: Um olhar desde a Educação Matemática. *Revista Latinoamericana de Etnomatemática*, 10(3), 39–58.
- Viola dos Santos, J. R., & Buriasco, R. L. C. (2008). Da ideia de erro para as maneiras de lidar: Caracterizando nossos alunos pelo que eles têm e não pelo que lhes falta. In R. L. C. de Buriasco (Eds.), *Avaliação e educação matemática* (pp. 87–107). SBEM.
- Viola dos Santos, J. R., Barbosa, E. P., & Linardi, P. R. (2018). Formação de professores de matemática e atividades baseadas em categorias do cotidiano. *Vidya*, 38, 39–57.
- Walsh, C. (2009). *Interculturalidad, estado, sociedad: Luchas (de)coloniales de nuestra época*. Ediciones Abya-Yala.
- Walsh, C. (2013). Lo pedagógico y lo decolonial: Entrejendo caminos. In C. Walsh (Ed.), *Pedagogías decoloniales: Prácticas insurgentes de resistir, (re)existir, y (re)vivir* (pp. 23–68). Abya-Yala.